

SUSTAINING RESEARCH CULTURE THROUGH DEVELOPING ACADEMIC WRITING SKILLS AMONG SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS AT BAUAN TECHNICAL HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

Department of Education through the R.A. 10533, the Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum emphasizes that writing is not merely an option but a necessity for it contributes to academic success in this globally competitive information age. This study purports to develop the students' academic writing skills since this can help students in evaluating, analyzing, and synthesizing the collected data and information of their research. It intends to provide a series of remedial sessions about academic writing to guide the students in their research journey. Through a self-made questionnaire, the extent of utilization of the academic writing skills in practical research writing such as planning, style, document specifications, organization and accuracy of information were assessed. The significant differences of the assessment were then evaluated in accordance with their gender, strand, performance in English for Academic Professional Purposes and Practical Research Writing 1. Findings revealed that most of the Senior High School student-respondents are females, from Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) strand, had Very satisfactory grade in both English for Academic and Professional Purposes and Practical Research 1 subjects. Accuracy as an academic writing skill was assessed by the students to a great extent. The assessment of the extent of utilization of the academic writing skills do not have significant difference as to gender. As to strand, only Document Specification was not found to have significant difference while there is a difference on the other skills. Planning, Document Specifications and Accuracy of Information were assessed not to have significant difference while Style and Organization were found to have significant difference when grouped according to performance in English for Academic and Professional Purposes. The researchers aimed that this study embarks on sustaining research culture in Bauan Technical High School which had been one of their focuses since Senior High School Program started.

Keywords: Research Culture, Academic Writing Skills, Senior High School, Practical Research, English for Academic, Philippines/Asia